

Transform to OPen Science Training (TOPST; F.14 of ROSES-22) Frequently Asked Questions

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Q1: What is TOPST?

A1: TOPST stands for “Transform to Open Science Training.” The F.14 TOPST program element can be found [here](#). TOPST element solicits proposals for; (1) the development of the [ScienceCore](#), a discipline specific scientific use cases curriculum, (2) implementation of Summer Schools to teach OpenCore, and (3) implementation of Virtual Cohorts to complete OpenCore. The training material as well as the design of the learning activities should be targeted to audiences from undergraduate students to established scientists and managers from all science disciplines supported by NASA’s Science Mission Directorate (SMD).

Q2: What is the difference between OpenCore and ScienceCore?

A2: TOPS has set itself the goal of meeting everyone where they are at in their open science journey. The core open science curriculum, or OpenCore, is currently being developed and will be available by April 1, 2023. OpenCore will introduce open science principles and practices to those who have not yet engaged deeply with open science. More details about OpenCore can be found [here](#). In contrast, the ScienceCore focuses on how open science can be used to generate new hypotheses and how to apply open science to particular disciplines. Areas of focus for the ScienceCore include how to access and analyze NASA science data including cloud-based data; open-source data, analysis, and visualization libraries both general and discipline-specific libraries; and creation, management, and sharing of reproducible science workflows and results. ScienceCore components may extend OpenCore concepts or cover SMD foundational discipline-specific themes leveraging, where possible, existing NASA cloud-based datasets. Both OpenCore and ScienceCore final products will be permissively licensed and contributed to the NASA [TOPS GitHub](#).

Q3: What are “summer schools” and “virtual cohorts”? Why are they different?

A3: Summer Schools are in-person or hybrid meetings that are designed to assist NASA’s SMD science teams complete OpenCore and earn the TOPS Open Science certification. The TOPS open science curriculum, [OpenCore](#), must be taught during summer school. In contrast, virtual cohorts are online workshops designed to assist individuals complete OpenCore and earn their TOPS Open Science certification.

Individuals may have started the OpenCore MOOC online but require support to complete. Other individuals may have taken one or more OpenCore modules at an in-person workshop but require assistance to complete the curriculum. The proposal does not specify exactly how this will be done as there could be many different models that help learners complete the curriculum. For example, virtual cohorts could teach the in-person workshop materials during virtual workshops. Another example could be that virtual cohorts consist of learners completing the online MOOC curriculum, but are seeking a community with which to discuss the information as well as ask questions. Virtual Cohorts will help online learners find that community, encourage completion of the online course, and help facilitate learning. Although Summer Schools can also be held hybrid, they differ from Virtual Cohorts in that Summer Schools are taught by an instructor (or several instructors) in an in-person “classroom” setting. Virtual Cohorts are primarily online, either through regular workshops or self-paced, with group enrichment and discussion held periodically.

Q4: Are there any requirements for the selection of summer school locations?

A4: Priority will be placed on proposals that hold activities at or heavily involve non-R1 Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCU), Hispanic Serving Institutions (HSI) and Tribal Colleges and Universities (TCU) or have previously held similar activities that have documented participation and sustained engagement by underrepresented communities.

Q5: What review process will be used to evaluate the TOPST proposals?

A5: Dual-anonymous peer review process: not only are proposers unaware of the identity of the members on the review panel, but the reviewers do not have explicit knowledge of the proposal teams during the scientific evaluation of the proposal. More information is available at <https://science.nasa.gov/researchers/dual-anonymous-peer-review>

Q6: Should proposals include an Open-Source Science Development Plan or an Equal Access Plan?

A6: All proposals must submit an Open-Source Science Development Plan that describes how project materials will be openly available. Summer Schools and Virtual Cohorts proposals must also submit an Equal Access Plan. The Open-Source Science Development Plan must conform to [Earth Science Division guidelines](#). Please see the F.14 program element for more details. The Equal Access Plans are described in F.14 Section 4.2.1. Here we provide some useful references:

- NASA’s Mission Equity initiative: <https://www.nasa.gov/mission-equity>
- Accessibility requirements for information and communication technology: <https://www.access-board.gov/ict/>

- Universal Design and Accessibility:
<https://www.section508.gov/develop/universal-design/>

Q7: Open-Source Science Development plans are usually not included within the S/T/M page limit. Does that also apply to the Equity Access Plan?

A7: Neither the Open-Source Science Development plan nor the Equity Access Plan are counted in the S/T/M page limit. In addition to the 10 pages per topic for the S/T/M section, one additional page is allotted for the Proposal Summary, two additional pages are allotted for the anonymized Open-Source Science Development Plan (see Section 4.1), and, for Summer Schools and Virtual Cohorts proposals only, two additional pages are allocated for the anonymized Equal Access Plan (see Section 4.2.1).

Q8: Who is able to propose for funding for TOPST?

A7: Organizations of every type, domestic and foreign, Government and private, for-profit and not-for-profit, may submit proposals without restriction on teaming arrangements, other than with China, see subsection (c). See Section III of the [ROSES-2022 Summary of Solicitation for subsection \(c\) and more details.](#)

Q9: Can non-U.S. institutions submit proposals?

A9: Proposals from non-U.S. institutions are welcome, but they must be on a no-exchange-of-funds basis. Funding may not be requested to support activities at non-US institutions but may be requested to support activities at US institutions, e.g., for funding a Co-Investigator at a U.S. institution. In other words, non-U.S. institutions may submit the proposal as a lead organization but may not request or receive any funds directly to them; it can be used to support US institutions or partners.

Q10: Does a PI have to be a US citizen? Are green card holders eligible?

A10: ROSES does not require either citizenship nor green card if the work is not export controlled. Your organization likely has rules about who may serve as PI. Eligibility is covered in Section III of the [ROSES-2022 Summary of Solicitation. There is no discussion of PI citizenship requirements in that section.](#)

Q11: May a for-profit apply (and be the lead) for this grant?

A11: Yes, a for-profit may be the lead for a proposal to this program element. Please see the [NASA Guidebook for Proposers](#) for further details.

Q12: Is it permissible to submit more than one proposal?

A12: Yes.

Q13: If an organization submits more than one proposal, does it need to be for different elements of the call? Or can we have more than one proposal for the same element (for example, more than one proposal for ScienceCore, Summer Schools, or Virtual Cohorts)?

A13: Organizations may submit multiple proposals for the same element, but each proposal is limited to a single element.

Q14: How frequently will this be solicited?

A14: This is the first time a solicitation of this scope has been released. At this time, we do not plan to solicit this as part of ROSES23, and the frequency of the program element will be determined only after review of this program element.

Q15: How many awards will be given for each type of proposal?

A14: The number of proposals selected will be dependent on the number and quality of proposals submitted and on the availability of funds. See table below.

	ScienceCore Curriculum	Summer Schools	Virtual Cohorts
Total Budget	**\$1.3 million per year	**\$1.2 million per year	**\$400,000 per year
Duration	Max 2 years	Max 3 years	Max 3 years
# of Projects	6-12	3-4	2-3

** Total budget divided across projects

Q16: What would be an appropriate project start date?

A16: A start date beginning sometime between May and June 2023 would be reasonable.

Q17: Is there any restriction on the number of Co-Investigators?

A17: There are no restrictions on the number of Co-investigators.

Q18: Are there restrictions/benefits to including undergraduate student involvement for academic institutions?

A18: There are no restrictions on inclusion of undergraduate students, and you can consider the inclusion aspect of their involvement.

Q19: Normally Collaborators are unfunded and Co-Investigators are funded. Is that not the case here?

A19: As stated on p. 34 of the [NASA Guidebook for Proposers](#), a Co-Investigator may or may not receive funding through the award. And, p. 35 states that a Collaborator is unfunded.

Q20: Is there any template for this program element?

A20: No.

Q21: What will the expected clearance process be for any materials and code developed? Will it need to go through NASA's software clearance?

A21: Material developed as part of a selected proposal should go through the proposing organizations release process. This process and the materials should be described in the Open Source Science plan. While restricted material such as export control may be described, the developed material should not contain any restricted information. Materials will not go through any NASA software clearance unless the proposing organization is a NASA center.

Q22: The program element indicates that proposers should describe activities to be performed with workshop and/or virtual cohort participants. When referring to "activities," would that be synchronous learning engagements, asynchronous learning, or a mix of the two? Similarly, are there restrictions on whether these activities are in-person, hybrid, or virtual?

A22: Capacity-building activities in this program element are Summer School and Virtual Cohorts both to support learners earning the TOPS Open Science Badge by completing all five *OpenCore* modules. The activities to support the workshops should be described by the proposers. Proposals are not limited to traditional, e.g., in-person meetings. The narrative should indicate whether the activity is totally in-person or virtual or hybrid.

Q23: May proposals be written in collaboration with folks at different universities?

A23: Yes, you may have collaborators and Co-Investigators from other organizations.

Q24: May graduate students serve as principal investigators (PIs) either with or without a faculty advisor?

A24: Yes, ROSES does not specify who at an organization may be a PI, but organizations may have restrictions.

Q25: What is the intended audience of the ScienceCore? How about the virtual cohorts and summer schools? Is this audience anticipated to be geographically distributed and diverse?

A25: The training materials, as well as the design of the learning activities, must be targeted to audiences from undergraduate students to established scientists and managers from all science disciplines supported by SMD.

Q26: Is it advantageous to apply as a team of organizations? Or as an individual institution? For instance, would it be better for a for-profit proposer team with a nonprofit?

A26: The solicitation does not have any teaming requirements. It is up to the PI to determine the best possible team.

Q27: How much will the TOPS team help facilitate communication among the project teams chosen?

A27: Funded TOPST projects must work in a collaborative open fashion. Proposals should include a plan for attendance at an annual 4-day TOPS coordination meeting in Washington DC.

Q28: Would the F.14 call be applicable for creating training programs designed to train high school STEM instructors in using NASA datasets as part of their curriculum? For example, teaching instructors how to use the GeneLab database.

A28: This call is not intended to expand to the K-12 audience.

Q29: Are proposals for “science enabling platforms” appropriate for this call?

A29: Proposals for “science enabling platforms” are not appropriate for this call. This program element seeks applications from entities to support the following three activities:

- (1) Development of ScienceCore materials (see Section 3.1),
- (2) Implementation of summer schools (see Section 3.2.1), and
- (3) Virtual cohorts (see Section 3.2.2).

Q30: Could funds from this call be used to adapt existing open science training materials for a particular discipline and thus for the ScienceCore?

A30: As long as it meets all the requirements described in Sections 3.1 and 4.1 of the TOPST program element text.

Q31: For the ScienceCore curriculum topic, are the grantees responsible for developing an online portal or integrating their work into an existing online platform? In other

words, is it just developing curriculum materials, or does it also include getting them online into one of the systems?

A31: There is no requirement to develop an online portal as part of this program element. Modules will either be integrated into the TOPS Open edX platform or be interactive Jupyter Books hosted on the TOPS GitHub. It will be important for proposals to detail what their notebooks or other materials would require.

Q32: Would the training be focusing on datasets or open-source tools?

A32: We are specifically soliciting curricula that focus on any of the following topics:

- How to access and analyze NASA science data including cloud-based data.
- Core open-source data, analysis, and visualization libraries both general and discipline-specific libraries.
- Creation, management, and sharing of reproducible science workflows and results.

Proposers must review and align the ScienceCore curriculum use cases to the specific themes that are currently priorities for SMD Divisions (see section 3.1).

Q33: Does the ScienceCore materials have to use NASA datasets, or could any openly-available dataset be used?

A33: We are specifically soliciting curricula that focus on how to access and analyze NASA science data including NASA cloud-based data. Virtual cohorts should be designed to provide additional support, facilitate, and encourage completion of the TOPS OpenCore.

Q34: Would TOPS F.14 be an appropriate venue to develop a course on teaching open science practices in physics to undergraduate students?

A34: The training materials must be targeted to audiences from undergraduate students to established scientists and managers from all science disciplines supported by SMD.

Q35: For in person summer schools, is it expected that the award covers all the travel and lodging costs for participants as well as the proposal team?

A35: It is not expected that the award covers all the travel and lodging costs for all the participants. Selectees for this activity may include the costs for the proposal team and for participation (including travel) for 5-10 graduate student/early career scientists per meeting.

Q36: Will the summer schools be using a MOOC platform? If so, will TOPS be providing one?

A36: Summer Schools should be taught in-person or have a hybrid format. Although the OpenCore materials will be on the MOOC platform Open edX, the summer schools are

likely to use the in-person OpenCore workshop materials. Proposals should detail how they intend to teach the OpenCore content, and the technology requirements of that plan, if any.

Q37: During the Summer School workshops, would only the OpenCore be taught or could elements of the ScienceCore also be taught? If the ScienceCore were being taught, would a separate proposal need to be submitted describing the course?

A37: As the ScienceCore may not be available during Summer 2023, Summer Schools are expected only to be teaching OpenCore for the first year of the program. ScienceCore material may be included, if appropriate, once it is available.

Q38: How large should the virtual cohorts be? In other words, is the vision breadth (reaching a lot of people very quickly) or depth (reaching only a few but providing them with a deep understanding)?

A38: The selectee(s) has flexibility in organizing activities, but it is expected that all five modules will be taught to virtual cohorts throughout the year, completing the entire curriculum 5 - 8 times (25 - 40 virtual activities per year). TOPS is open to proposals with both a “breadth” and a “depth” approach. Proposals should specify the size that they have in mind, the technology requirements of that size, and a plan for engagement and moderation at scale.

Q39: For virtual cohort construction, will there be opportunities to partner directly with NASA and the TOPS team to recruit participants for these cohorts? Or should the grant include mechanisms for advertising and marketing these efforts, and expect to take full responsibility for cohort construction?

A39: The TOPS team will assist the selectees with identifying participants or science teams for the summer schools and virtual cohorts. Outreach activities will also be important. The selectee(s) has flexibility in organizing activities, but it is expected that all five modules will be taught to virtual cohorts throughout the year, completing the entire curriculum 5 - 8 times (25 - 40 virtual activities per year).

Q40: Is the priority of the virtual cohorts to facilitate completion of the OpenCore curriculum first-and-foremost?

A40: Yes, the priority for the virtual cohorts is to help facilitate the completion of OpenCore (all five modules) and provide additional support through coordinated activities to build an open science community.

Q41: For summer schools and virtual cohorts, is there a specific focus on US vs non-US participants?

A.41 Summer Schools are designed to assist NASA's SMD science teams in the US. For geographic locations, proposers are encouraged to choose a U.S. location, e.g., 50 U.S. states, the District of Columbia, commonwealths and territories, and tribal lands within the United States. The proposal should explain why a non-U.S. location is justified. For more details see section, 3.2.3 Logistics for Summer Schools and Virtual Cohorts.

Q42: May foreign team members be supported via this program element?

A42: Short plain English answer: NASA funds research at US institutions and foreign agencies pay for research at foreign institutions. Thus, the rules focus on the institution, not the individual. If your institution hires this foreign investigator, then you can pay him/her while they are in your employ. If the foreign investigator does not have a position at a US institution, then NASA funds may not be used to support them, not even for travel. The longer answer and the more official version of this may be found in the NASA Guidebook for Proposers, Section 3.2 "Submission Requirements and Restrictions".

Q43: What are the acceptable topics for virtual cohort curriculums?

A43: The virtual cohorts are to help facilitate the completion of the existing [OpenCore](#) curriculum (all five modules).

For general FAQs related to ROSES-2022 see <https://science.nasa.gov/researchers/sara/faqs>

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